

Research-in-Progress Paper

Campus as a Living Lab for Sustainability: Learning from Change Agents at Utrecht University

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Abstract

This research provides insights into how a university campus can operationalize living labs to facilitate sustainability transitions. By offering an in-depth investigation of Utrecht University (UU) and the Centre for Living Labs (CLU), the study aims to explore the operationalization of campus living labs (CLL) as a transformative tool in research, education, institutional practices, and stakeholder engagement for advancing systemic change toward sustainability. The study asks: How do actors at UU engage with the CLLs in practice to advance sustainability transitions? How do CLLs support universities in achieving their overarching sustainability goals? Drawing from interviews that are held during a visiting research period at UU, the study incorporates a qualitative analysis with three major actor groups that became change agents in UU's sustainability journey and focus on the CLL operations to learn from their insights on how sustainability is framed, negotiated, and implemented through CLLs at the institution, eventually to find out how much the university's education and research focus is aligned with the sustainability goals in CLL operations.

Keywords

Campus as a living lab, sustainability transitions, co-creation, qualitative analysis, higher education institutions

Introduction

In light of escalating environmental, social, and economic challenges that bring deeper issues to overcome, especially in densely populated urban areas, higher education institutions (HEIs) are increasingly gaining importance to become critical drivers of transformative innovation for sustainability transitions (Villa et al., 2020). Lately, as recent studies and policies indicate a shift towards more rationalized, societal, and solution-oriented approaches for scientific research, more higher education institutions (HEIs), sometimes interchangeably phrased as universities, are reforming their strategies toward open science. Integrating open science as a new anchor in their education and research environment, more universities focus on assigning students more challenge-based learning projects to encourage society-oriented research toward social impact.

Focusing on societal impact and producing useful knowledge in terms of accessibility, universities have an important role in being the knowledge and innovation centres on local, regional, and even national scales. Being a part of the National Innovation System (NIS) and, more importantly, creating the production of knowledge workers is setting a wider definition for the role of universities in science-based innovation (Lundvall, 2007; Purcell et al., 2019; Villa et al., 2020). And with the help of the emerging "Campus as a Living Lab" (CLL) framework, academic institutions are uniquely positioned to lead in the co-creation of sustainable and resilient urban futures (Rogers et al., 2023; Herth et al., 2024; Hadfield et al., 2025).

Living labs, both as a method and a place of experimentation, seek to improve collaboration, inclusivity, and collective knowledge through co-creation and co-learning processes in physical or virtual spaces. They are used in all forms of their generations in the milieu of governance (Dekker et al., 2020; Ruijter & Meijer, 2020), environmental practices (Ahmed et al., 2017; Evans et al., 2015; Liedtke et al., 2012), and urban innovation research (Bergvall-Kåreborn & Ståhlbröst, 2009; Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012; Bourcet, 2017; Nesti, 2018; Veeckman & Schuurman, 2013). Since the number of related articles started to increase in the mid-2010s, it is possible to define that living labs have been a hot topic of discussion for sustainability practices recently (Hossain et al., 2019; Howarth et al., 2022; W. Leal Filho et al., 2020).

This study touches upon how HEIs, leveraging their spatial, intellectual, and social resources, act as arenas for experimentation and collaboration to address pressing urban challenges. The concept of CLL redefines campuses as microcosms of urban systems, integrating research, education, and community engagement to test and implement

innovative solutions in real-world contexts. This study examines the potential of HEIs to foster systemic change by acting as platforms for co-learning, participatory governance, and the co-design of resilient urban strategies. Central to this inquiry is the role of universities as agents that bridge academia, public institutions, industry, and local communities, thereby situating themselves as pivotal drivers in sustainability actions and, hence, more pragmatically, the UNDP's SDGs.

Taking the CLLs as the common denominator, this study focuses on the case of Utrecht University (UU) and its Centre for Living Labs (CLU) operational body that facilitates the CLLs mainly in the Science Park (Uithof) Campus, Utrecht, the Netherlands. Utrecht University, one of Europe's internationally renowned universities and the oldest HEI in the Netherlands, is among the institutions that use the CLLs for sustainability transitions at both the institutional, local, regional, and global levels. While it is clearly stated in UU's Strategic Plan for 2025, as five guiding principles of [1] collaboration across borders, [2] a future-proof teaching culture, [3] a close-knit community, [4] a focus on sustainable development, and [5] the transition to open science, less is known about how these ambitions are experienced and interpreted by the actors of UU (2025).

To examine the tensions and interoperability of CLLs, this study employs a qualitative analytical approach to navigate between three main stakeholder groups on UU for academic (institutional) ambitions and sustainability ambitions. The study asks: *How do actors at UU engage with the CLLs in practice to advance sustainability transitions, and in what ways do they become change agents? How do CLLs support universities in achieving their overarching sustainability goals?*

Methodology

This study focuses on the novel concept of living labs that are facilitated by Utrecht University, aiming to identify the academic and sustainability contributions of campus living labs. In order to analyse the complex entanglement of CLLs in UU, and in the Science Park campus in particular, within the context of education, research, policymaking, governance, transition studies, and societal impact, a variety of qualitative analysis methods were employed. These included in-depth interviews, thematic coding, and document analysis. In addition, the research involved a comprehensive review of prior studies to situate the evolution of living labs in their institutional and historical context. Methodologically, the study draws on the principles of action-based and phronetic social research to critically examine power relations, practical outcomes, and value-driven change (Flyvbjerg, 2001).

Semi-structured interviews are being held to analyse actors who are either involved in or influence the processes of CLLs at Utrecht University. The categorization was made on three levels for these interviews:

1. Academic and administrative staff who are related to the history and evolution of UU and the sustainability initiatives of the university, but have no direct link with the CLLs or coordination
2. The central coordination team that comprises the Centre for Living Labs
3. The experts/researchers from active and inactive living labs CLLs

Each party has been asked slightly different questions regarding their perception of projects, the university's sustainability actions and working towards the SDGs. Each group got to answer 9-11 questions for their interviews, which approximately took an hour. Participants have been selected through a process of actor mapping and snowballing. They were informed beforehand with consent forms, and they have given consent to proceed with audio recordings, which will be deleted after the publishing phase of the doctoral dissertation. To highlight certain themes in the qualitative analysis of the case study, the questions were intricately organized to follow a specific pattern of ambitions, approach, supportive environment, outcomes, and broader perspective. These categories pave the way for analysing CLLs in a concise but more elaborate way. They are later incorporated into the thematic coding using the NVivo software. In addition to the mother codes, several child codes are added to deepen the coding. To reflect on the general conflicts and contradictory narratives between the five main themes, the mother code “tensions” was added. The tensions code mostly overlapped with certain thematic coding, which indicated the conflict areas in the CLLs.

To analyse the in-depth interviews, the NVivo software program for qualitative analysis is being used. The selected three interviews from the three focus groups are coded with six non-hierarchical mother codes and some child codes as listed below:

1. Ambitions

- Academic ambitions
- Sustainability ambitions
- Transition studies (theoretical ambitions)

2. Approach

- Limitations of living labs

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- Methods
3. Broader perspective
- Networks
 - Societal impact
4. Outcomes
- Limitations
 - Scaling
5. Supportive environment
- Interdisciplinary collaboration
 - Policy and management
 - Stakeholder engagement
6. Tensions

Using transcribed documents of interviews, every document was coded within the themes, and the mother codes aggregated the codes from the child codes. Within the NVivo interface, the matrix coding query was used to identify certain issues, as you can investigate further below.

Figure 1. Matrix coding scheme for interview analysis

Preliminary Findings

For the first draft of this chapter, three interviewees from three different actor groups have been selected to be analysed.

- 1) From group 1, a staff member from the university's sustainability management (Sustainability Office) was selected.
- 2) From group 2, a member of the core team of the Centre for Living Labs was selected.
- 3) From group 3, one of the experts from the living lab projects was selected.

Table 1. MCQ 1, Compare Codes Across Interview Groups

	A : Group1_1	B : Group2_1	C : Group3_1
1 : Ambitions	13	12	21
2 : Academic Ambitions	8	5	9
3 : Sustainability Ambitions	3	4	10
4 : Transition studies- theoretical ambitions	5	3	4
5 : Approach	4	12	12
6 : Limitations of living labs	2	5	6
7 : Methods	2	7	8
8 : Broader Perspective	3	8	8
9 : Networks	0	3	7
10 : Societal impact	3	5	1
11 : Outcomes	7	6	2
12 : Limitations	4	2	0
13 : Scaling	3	4	2
14 : Supportive Environment	14	23	22
15 : Interdisciplinary collaboration	4	4	1
16 : Policy and Management	6	9	11
17 : Stakeholder Engagement	4	11	10
18 : Tensions	0	8	3

Table 2: MCQ 2, Identify co-occurrence of themes

	A : Tensions
1 : Ambitions	2
2 : Academic Ambitions	1
3 : Sustainability Ambitions	1

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4 : transition studies- theoretical ambitions	0
5 : Approach	3
6 : Limitations of living labs	3
7 : Methods	0
8 : Broader Perspective	0
9 : Networks	0
10 : Societal impact	0
11 : Outcomes	0
12 : Limitations	0
13 : Scaling	0
14 : Supportive Environment	5
15 : Interdisciplinary collaboration	0
16 : Policy and Management	4
17 : Stakeholder Engagement	1

Table 3. MCQ 3, Compare child nodes in “ambitions”

	Academic Ambitions	Sustainability Ambitions
A : Group1_1	8	3
B : Group2_1	5	4
C : Group3_1	9	10

Preliminary findings reveal actors’ perspectives from different stakeholder groups related to the UU’s sustainability initiatives, with the CLU core team emphasizing systemic change towards a more operationalized living labs structure on campus. While the expert group of LL researchers prioritizes more localized solutions for CLLs, they also tend to go back to the conventional ways of “testing” and “experimenting” on campus grounds. This exposes tensions between institutional rhetoric and campus grassroots actions. However, the multi-stakeholder, innovative, transformative, participatory, and non-linear approach embedded in the real-life context of CLLs does not allow the project to steer towards a structured, top-down, goal-oriented, and deductive way.

The interviewee A defined the core functions of the university as education, research, and societal transformation, which indicates a strong sense of engagement with the community. Findings show participants critiquing top-down sustainability actions and advocating participatory and bottom-up processes with co-creation, integrating students

in the process of living labs for better learning experiences. However, the case study's limitations include a small sample size (n=19 interviews for UU) and a single case focus with limited assessment.

Discussion and Conclusion

This study makes an original contribution to the literature by drawing insights from sustainability actors at Utrecht University, who are realizing the campus as a living lab on various levels and becoming change agents for sustainability transitions. While CLU operates as a mediator and facilitator in the realization of CLLs on campus with stakeholders, narratives on sustainability from different actors sometimes create tension in living lab governance. By dissecting the relations, this study proposes an understanding of the CLL model to achieve sustainable campuses, provide value to researchers, policymakers, and higher education institutions, and address environmental challenges in urban areas.

The current analysis is based on a first round of interviews and thematic coding. One of the key insights from this study's analysis is that CLLs, in terms of their level of engagement with technology and society, are not simply infrastructures of technology or management but rather discursive and spatial arenas that are transformative by nature. By participating in the co-creation processes of living labs, the actors become change agents for sustainability transitions within and beyond the campus. Drawing on Lefebvre's (1991) spatial trialectics, the CLLs can be understood as a space where conceived (institutional visions for global sustainability goals), perceived (material and operational practices), and lived (everyday experiences, innovation models) spaces intersect and sometimes conflict. This spatial interplay reveals how CLLs can construct and deconstruct institutional narratives as the campus becomes a playground for negotiation and transformation for better futures.

Finally, this study contributes to the growing literature and modelling of university campuses as living labs for a future where different forms of collaboration, experimentation, and co-creation are preliminary for addressing societal and environmental challenges. Future research could compare CLU with other CLL examples around the world to identify transferable governance models for enhancing sustainability at HEIs.

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